

CINIE 2022

DEPARTAMENTO DE TECNOLOGÍA DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

23TH, 24TH and 25TH March 2022

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
Avda. Juan de Herrera, 6-28040-MADRID

International
Conference of
Educational
Innovation in
Building

*Congreso
Internacional de
Innovación
Educativa en
Edificación*

LIBRO DE ACTAS
ABSTRACTS BOOK

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN

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Educational Innovation in Technical Education	López Zaldívar, Óscar Gil López, Tomás
Equal Opportunities for Women in Research and Teaching	Valiente López, Mercedes Vidales Barriguete, Alejandra
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New Trends in Education	Álvarez Dorado, Manuel Saiz Martínez, Pablo García Fernández Pacheco, Daniel
Research in Education and Human Development	Saez Pérez, M ^a Paz Verdú Vázquez, Amparo
Research in Education: Educational Innovation	Borrás Gené, Oriol Ferrández Vega, Daniel Ríos Aguilar, Sergio José

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MAQUETACIÓN Y DISEÑO / DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

Herrero del Cura, Sofía
Lozano Díez, Rafael Vicente
Martínez Rodríguez, Mar (Diseño Web)

GREETINGS**VI INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION IN BUILDING****(CINIE 2022)****23, 24 y 25 de marzo de 2022**

This new edition of the CINIE, the sixth one, aims to lay the foundations for the development of joint projects and produce relevant results in the field of educational innovations in higher education. With the primary objective of continuous improvement in the teaching methodology within the building field, it is intended to include the latest advances and research in the field of teaching-learning, which contributes to the production of scientific results of quality of international interest.

The organization of CINIE 2022 programme contains different activities in innovation in educational methods, oral communications, posters and virtual exhibitions of different thematic areas such as advances in educational research, New tendencies in university education and other different fields, as well as differentiated actions in the BIM environment

In this sixth edition, it is important to note the quality and involvement of all participants, which has led to the presentation of a large number of papers that group more than 175 speakers from different places through their different typologies of Presentations.

The Organizing Committee

Thursday, 24th March 2022/ Morning conferences

Hall of Degrees

Conferences		SESSION 2 (PRESENTIAL SESSION) Chair: Daniel Ferrández Vega
10:00 – 10:20	(023) VENEZUELA. CONSTRUCTION PROBLEMS AND SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION. COLLECTING DATA TO PUT THE PUZZLE TOGETHER. Part 1. Licia Pietrosevoli de Dikdan; Carlos Rodríguez-Monroy; Yilsy Nuñez Guerrero	
10:20 – 10:40	(029) AUTOMATING THE CREATION OF VR EXPERIENCES AS LEARNING PILLS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR María Jesús Bopp; Felipe Muñoz La Rivera; Cayetano Sierra Martí; Javier Mora Serrano	
10:40 – 11:00	(064) SMATH STUDIO: WRITING, MATHEMATICAL CALCULATION, PLOTTING AND PROGRAMMING FREE TOOL Jorge Pablo Díaz Velilla; Guadalupe Dorado Escribano; Alberto Morón; Alicia Zaragoza	
11:00 – 11:20	(024) A SERVICE-LEARNING EXPERIENCE OF COLLABORATION BETWEEN THE UNIVERSITY AND SECONDARY EDUCATION TO PROMOTE VOCATIONS IN STEM STUDIES Sergio Blanco; Belén Muñoz-Medina; Marcos G. Alberti; Alejandro Enfedaque; María Teijeiro	

11:30-12:30

Poster session 2 + coffee break

Hall of Degrees

Conferences		SESSION 3 (PRESENTIAL SESSION) Chair: M ^a Paz Sáez Pérez
12:30-12:50	(016) HYBRID DIGITAL IDENTITY WORKSHOP USING INTERACTIVE TOOLS Oriol Borrás-Gené	
12:50-13:10	(039) LEARNING ACTIVITIES FOR SUSTAINABLE HUMAN DEVELOPMENT COORDINATED FOR THE PROJECT MODULE: COMPOSITION, PROJECTS AND URBANISM Iballa Naranjo Henríquez; Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez	
13:10-13:30	(019) TEACHING LAB EQUIPMENT COMMISSIONING FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE MECHANICAL VENTILATION CLASSES BASED ON LEARNING BY DOING METHODOLOGY AND OPEN SOURCE TRENDS Alexander Martín-Garín; José Antonio Millán-García; Cristina Marieta-Gorriti; Iñigo Rodríguez-Vidal; Nacim Alilat; Abderrahmane Baïri	
13:30-13:50	(020) TFM OR PFC. TIME CONSTRICTION, COLLECTIVE WORK AND PROGRAMMATIC FREEDOM AT THE ETSAM José Francisco García-Sánchez; Sergio Martin Blas	

GLOCAL II, 24th March 2022

GLOCAL - Innovative training of future engineers responding to problems of contemporary cities
GLOCAL - Formación innovadora de los futuros ingenieros que responde a los problemas de las ciudades contemporáneas
Erasmus+ 2019-1-PL01-KA203-065654
<https://glocal.pb.edu.pl/en/>

12:30 p.m. to 13:30 p.m., ETSEM – UPM

- Pilar Izquierdo Gracia: "GLOCAL: Summer Schools". **10 min.**
- M^a Aurora Flórez de la Colina: "GLOCAL: Some preliminary results of an Erasmus + Project, developed under an international pandemic". **10 min.**
- Dorota Gawryluk: "GLOCAL. Future of the city". **10 min.**
- Jurga Kučinskienė: "GLOCAL Glossary: an innovative learning tool to train future engineers in Europe". **10 min.**
- Alejandra Vidales: "GLOCAL – Sustainable cities", at ETSEM-UPM". **10 min.**

Questions and Discussion - Preguntas /Debate. **10 min.**

Innovative training of future engineers responding to problems of contemporary cities, Erasmus+ 2019-1-PL01-KA203-065654
Formación innovadora de los futuros ingenieros, que responde a los problemas de las ciudades contemporáneas
Escuela Técnica Superior de Edificación de Madrid, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid,
Sala de Juntas (ETSEM - UPM), Avda. Juan de Herrera, 6 – 28040 Madrid, Spain

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LEARNING ACTIVITIES FOR SUSTAINABLE HUMAN DEVELOPMENT COORDINATED FOR THE PROJECT MODULE: COMPOSITION, PROJECTS AND URBANISM

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Keywords: *Educational innovation, Human development, Urban planning, Territory, Landscape*

Abstract

This article exposes the application of an innovative coordination methodology, through different activities, in matters of urban planning in the search to improve human development in the particular context of learning sustainable project dynamics at various scales.

The selected activities exposed are part of the subjects: Urban Areas and Sustainable Design, from the 2nd year, City Planning, from the 3rd year, City Workshop, taught in the 4th year, and Territory and Landscape Planning, from the 5th year of the degree. These four subjects are part of the urban planning sub-module (Table 1) included in the Design Module: Composition, Projects and Urban Planning [1], and are compulsory as subject matter of the specialty, within the degree in Fundamentals of Architecture.

These subjects have common general learning objectives, emphasizing obtaining knowledge of the planning mechanisms of the territory and the city, as well as the understanding and analysis of the relationships of territorial and urban planning with the geographical, socioeconomic, ecological and of environmental sustainability. From the transversality, it is sought that human development be integrated into the understanding of the concept of urban fact. In this way, the complexities of these notions are transcended to the actions of the various urban fabrics, functional models, economic realities and environmental challenges [2].

For this, coordination meetings were established prior to the beginning of the course between the teachers of the subjects, which served to deploy a series of learning activities agreed upon among them. Activities that have been developed through different experiential learning methodologies [3] such as Project-Based Learning -PBL- and Challenge-Based Learning -CBL-, as well as other methodologies such as cooperative learning, practice-based learning, in workshop teachings and in field experiences.

Are presented here the specific activities that have helped the development of transversal and general competences that allow linking the contents of the subjects with

human development at a local level, with specific territorial problems, and the Sustainable Development Goals -SDGs- [4] initiative promoted by the United Nations Organization worldwide.

Among the different training objectives of the module's subjects, is that students gradually delve into the complex challenges that the new millennium holds for humanity and acquire the largest number of response tools. This coordination has allowed and will allow students to acquire the necessary resources to prospect the complexity of the territory, taking into account sustainable development from the large scale to the local scale with appropriate interventions that guarantee human development.

Table 1: Submodule or urbanism of the Degree in Fundamentals of Architecture.

Curso	ECTS	Subject
1º	6	Urban Development Basics
2º	6	Urban Areas and Sustainable Design
3º	6	Urban Planning
4º	6	Project Workshop of the City
5º	6	Territory and Landscape Planning

Relation between the courses, the ECTS credits and the subjects of the submodule of urbanism.

References

- [1] Registro de Universidades Centros y Títulos. <https://www.educacion.gob.es/ruct/solicitud/datosModulo!consulta.action?codModulo=3&actual=menu.solicitud.planificacion.materias>, (acceso el 16 febrero 2022)
- [2] H.I. Naranjo Henríquez. Agotamiento del territorio. El caso de Gran Canaria. [Tesis Doctoral] Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), 2010.
- [3] P.M. De Souza Sánchez, R. Godoy Rodríguez. A.B.P. real de promoción de la arquitectura, el arte y la naturaleza de La Orotava. In: J. Sierra Sánchez, M. Antón Barco (Eds.), *De la Polis a la Urbe a través de miradas interdisciplinarias*. McGraw-Hill, 2021, pp. 715-740. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6372910> Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/11268/10900>
- [4] United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/es/sustainable-development-goals> (acceso el 16 febrero 2022)